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Palladium(II) Chloride Complexes of some Aryl Methyl Sulphides. Part-2. Substituent Effect on Pd—S and Pd—Cl Stretching Frequencies

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LOW frequency infrared spectra of the palladium(II) complexes of methyl phenyl sulphide as ligand have been recorded¹⁻³ and the stretching frequencies for Pd—S and Pd—Cl are assigned to be 294 and 370 cm⁻¹, respectively. The other intense band at 342 cm⁻¹ has been attributed³ to the asymmetric stretch for Pd—Cl. These spectral observations are in agreement with the assumption that the complex is trans-square-planar. Such square-planar complexes have been the subject of previous infrared investigations^{4,5}. In trans-complexes of palladium(II) only one metal-chlorine vibration would be ir-active and $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ stretch in the range 353–359 cm⁻¹ was noticed. In the present study, the infrared spectra of palladium(II) chloride complexes of several mono-, di-, and tri-substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides have been prepared⁶ and recorded in the region 900–200 cm⁻¹ and the $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$ stretching frequencies are assigned. The substituent effects over $\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ have been discussed.

Results and Discussion

The spectral assignments (Table 1) reveal that the complexes have trans-configuration (D_{2h} symmetry) and the data are in close agreement with those reported earlier^{1-3,7}. For the complex trans-PdCl₂(C₆H₅SCH₃)₂, two strong bands at 373 (asym) and 342 cm⁻¹ (sym) (the former being more intense than the latter) for Pd—Cl and a medium band at 298 cm⁻¹ for Pd—S are obtained. When the OCH₃ group is at *para*-position, the resonance effect outweighs the inductive effect which has a net electron-releasing tendency to the benzene ring, and so the Pd—S stretching frequency is decreased to a lower region (277 cm⁻¹) than that of the parent

compound. The OCH₃ in *meta*-position being an electron-withdrawing group, increased the Pd—S stretching frequency to a higher region as expected. The electron withdrawing NO₂ group at *para*-position attracts electrons through conjugative interaction and so the trans-PdCl₂(*p*-NO₂C₆H₄SCH₃) complex has its Pd—S stretching frequency at higher region (326 cm⁻¹) than its parent compound. Similarly, NO₂ in *meta*-position also acts as electron-withdrawing group. The halogen atoms in *para*-position are acting as electron-releasing group. This is obviously due to the presence of SCH₃ group in the *para*-position. Here sulphur is an electron acceptor and there is a possibility of the expansion of its valence shell. On the other hand, halogen atoms in *meta*-position acts as electron-withdrawing groups through inductive effect alone. The shift of OH band to the lower region (upto 40 cm⁻¹) in the complexes of hydroxy and carboxylic substituted phenyl methyl sulphides shows the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between OH and chlorine. The carbonyl frequency of *meta* and *para* carboxylic groups in their complexes gets increased when compared with the ligands. But in the case of *ortho*-isomer it is almost the same. This may be attributed to higher stability of the complexes having *meta* and *para* carboxylic substituted phenyl methyl sulphides when compared to the *ortho* isomer.

The behaviour of methoxy in the *ortho*-position is unexpected from the consideration of steric and increased inductive effects. In this case, the free rotation of methoxy group is restricted and increases its probability of attaining planarity with the benzene ring. Thus there can be enhanced resonance of methoxy group which outweighs its inductive effect. This may be the cause for steric enhancement of resonance and with the result the Pd—S stretching frequency decreases to 281 cm⁻¹. The frequency increase (319 cm⁻¹) in the complex dichlorobis(2,6-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphide)-palladium(II) is due to steric inhibition of resonance, as expected. The results of Pd—S stretching frequencies in complexes of *ortho*-substituted ligands show that the electronic effects as well as steric effects are operating. A strong σ -electron donor exerts a weakening effect on the M—S bond, and π -acceptor ligand removes the electron density from the metal⁸. It is generally found that all these substituted phenyl methyl sulphides are good trans-directing ligands. Some π -bonding between palladium and sulphur is also responsible for the trans-directing property of the ligands. Pure palladium(II) chloride exhibits Pd—Cl stretch at 337 cm⁻¹ as a strong band. This frequency moves to higher region in all the complexes. A perusal of the Pd—Cl frequencies of the complexes (Table 1) clearly shows that the Pd—Cl bonds are stronger in the complexes of *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulphides. The Pd—Cl strength in these complexes is in the order, *para* > *ortho* > *meta*. In aromatic

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TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{C-S}	ν_{Pd-Cl}	ν_{Pd-S}
PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ SCH ₃) ₂	727w	373s, 342s	298m
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727w	362s	312s
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727w	350ms	300ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	716mw	373s, 336s	288m
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	720m	356s	312m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	732w	350s	300w
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727s	373ms, 350s	281m
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	726m	358ms	312ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	738ms	360s	300m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	744mw	371m, 350s	265ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	731ms	361s	312ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	738s	346s	304mw
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724m	370m	326m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -COCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	723ms	358s	312ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727mw	360s	312m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724mw	350ms	297m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	720mw	363s	290mw
PdCl ₂ (2,6-di-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	719mw	361s	319ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	722m	362s, 335m	281m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724w	350s	310m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	722mw	367m, 350s	277ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	725mw	358m, 337m	250w
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724ms	356ms, 329w	250w
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -COOHC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724w	356s, 324w	310m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -COOHC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	720ms	354s	298ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -COOHC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	720ms	374s, 334s	305w
PdCl ₂ (4-OCH ₃ -3-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	719ms	351s	270mw
PdCl ₂ (3,5-di-CH ₃ -4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	724ms	374s, 334w	312vw

* In PdCl₂, ν_{Pd-Cl} = 337 cm⁻¹. vs = Very strong, s = strong, ms = medium strong, m = medium, mw = medium weak, w = weak, vw = very weak.

derivatives, the ν_{CSC} generally appears as a band of weak or moderate intensity in 702–673 cm⁻¹ region⁹. The increase in the ν_{CSC} is attributed to coordination from the sulphur atom.

Magnetic and Spectral Studies of Platinum(IV), Palladium(II) and Osmium(VI) Complexes with Thiodisuccinic Acid

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THE complexes of second and third row transition metal ions are interesting because of their enhanced stability, unusual magnetic properties and formation of bridges. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of platinum(IV), palladium(II) and osmium(VI) complexes with thiodisuccinic acid, HOOCCH₂CH(COOH)SCH(COOH)CH₂COOH (hereafter, TDSA). TDSA contains one sulphur atom and four carboxylic groups and is capable of combining with metal ions in various polydentate modes.

Experimental

Thiodisuccinic acid (Evans Chemetics, Inc., New York) of 98.1% purity was used as such without

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